

«So sa-a-a-ad that you're leaving». Making music with Auto-Tune, from Cher to vocal psychedelia

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Abstract

The pitch correction software Auto-Tune has become a pervasive feature in popular music on a global scale since its initial release in 1997. Despite its frequent dismissal as a device enabling those with limited vocal abilities to perform, Auto-Tune has been employed as an expressive tool from its earliest appearance on the music scene. The normalization of Auto-Tune in popular music practices can be observed both in the performance aspect, which regards the interaction between the singer and the software in real time, or at the production stage; and the reception aspect, which pertains to the impact of Auto-Tune on the aesthetic of contemporary pop voices. While there is a consensus regarding the influence of Auto-Tune on popular music over the past twenty-five years, reflections on this impact from a musicological perspective are scarce. Notably absent is any attempt to contextualize Auto-Tune as a device for making music, or a musical instrument in itself. This article aims to contribute to the existing literature on the subject matter by delineating a conceptual framework for understanding Auto-Tune as a defining technology in contemporary “musicking”, using the concept of “affordance”, and proposing an initial historicization and systematization of different musical practices and discourses regarding Auto-Tune.

“So sa-a-a-ad that you're leaving”. Fare musica con l'Auto-Tune, da Cher alla psichedelia vocale. Il software di pitch correction Auto-Tune è onnipresente nella popular music di tutto il mondo fin dal 1997. Nonostante sia stato spesso liquidato come “trucchetto” in grado consentire a performer poco dotati di cantare intonati, l'Auto-Tune è stato da subito impiegato come strumento espressivo. La normalizzazione dell'Auto-Tune nelle pratiche musicali popular riguarda sia l'aspetto della performance, nell'interazione tra il cantante e il software in tempo

reale o in fase di produzione, sia l'aspetto della ricezione, ovvero l'impatto dell'Auto-Tune sull'estetica delle voci pop contemporanee. Sebbene vi sia un generale consenso sull'influenza esercitata dall'Auto-Tune sulla popular music degli ultimi venticinque anni, le riflessioni da una prospettiva musicologica sono scarse, in particolare per quanto riguarda la comprensione dell'Auto-Tune come strumento per "fare musica", o come strumento musicale in sé. Questo articolo si propone di contribuire alla letteratura esistente delineando un quadro concettuale per comprendere l'Auto-Tune come tecnologia determinante nel musicking contemporaneo, utilizzando il concetto di "affordance" e proponendo una prima storicizzazione e sistematizzazione delle diverse pratiche musicali e dei discorsi che riguardano Auto-Tune.

1. Introduction

It's a technology that can make bad singers sound good and really bad singers [...] sound like robots. And it gives singers who sound like Kanye West or Cher the misplaced confidence that they too can croon. Thanks a lot, computers.

(Motivation for the inclusion of Auto-Tune among *Time Magazine's* «50 worst inventions of the modern era», Fletcher 2010)

It happened exactly 36 seconds into the song – a glimpse of the shape of pop to come, a feel of the fabric of the future we now inhabit. The phrase “I can't break through” turned crystalline, like the singer suddenly disappeared behind frosted glass. That sparkly special effect reappeared in the next verse, but this time a robotic warble wobbled, “So sa-a-a-ad that you're leaving.” [...] [W]hat we were really “leaving” was the 20th century.

(Reynolds 2018)

Since its first introduction in 1997, the pitch correction software Auto-Tune has become a ubiquitous feature in popular music on a global scale. While it has frequently been dismissed as a mere gimmick, designed to enable those with limited vocal abilities to perform, Auto-Tune has been employed as an expressive tool from as early as its appearance on the music scene. Its normalization in popular music practices concerns both the performance aspect, wherein the singer interacts with the software at the production stage, or in real time, anticipating its response in a feedback loop; and the reception aspect: it is impossible to ignore the impact of Auto-Tune on the aesthetic of contemporary pop voices, given its massive use in a range of contemporary musical genres. People sing *through* Auto-Tune, but also *with* Auto-Tune, or even *like* Auto-Tune, its digital glitches and robotic melismas providing a major model for vocalists all around the world.

While there is a consensus regarding the influence of Auto-Tune on popular music over the past twenty-five years, reflections on this impact from a musicological perspecti-

ve are scarce, and most notable is the absence of contributions seeking to contextualize Auto-Tune as a tool for making music, or even as a musical instrument (however atypical it may be).

This article aims to delineate a conceptual framework for conceptualizing Auto-Tune as a defining technology in contemporary «musicking» (Small 1998). To this end, its functioning will be examined in relation to the concept of “affordance”. An understanding of this outline cannot be achieved without considering the historical development of the different music practices involving Auto-Tune, as over the past 25 years it has been used in a multitude of ways, across a diverse range of musical genres, and for a variety of purposes.

Following the introduction, the second paragraph outlines some of the methodological challenges associated with the study of Auto-Tune. The subsequent paragraphs (3 and 4) address the advent of Auto-Tune, the affordances associated with the software's initial release, and its famed application in Cher's “Believe”. The study of musical practices and technologies must be conducted in close relation to the study of the discourses that influence and shape them. As Tilton (2008: 4) notes, «people make [music] in two ways [...] [t]hey produce the sounds they call music, and they also make music into a cultural domain, forming the ideas and activities they consider music». From the very beginning, Auto-Tune has been at the center of a network of conflicting discourses, central to the attribution of meaning to the various practices involving it: this topic is covered in paragraph 5. The second part of the essay historicizes the uses of Auto-Tune in vocal pop (6) and in its applications to speech and specifically rap music (7), up to its recent uses in mumble rap and other genres referred to as «vocal psychedelia» (Mackintosh K. 2021) (8).

2. Methodological issues: narratives, technologies, instruments and practices

In the history of music, the introduction of new sound technologies has been primarily examined in terms of its impact on the music itself. In narratives that emphasize the role of progress, the advent of new sound media and instruments (or enhancements to existing ones) are regarded as pivotal points of discontinuity, while the concept of “music” is conceived to evolve in accordance with a teleological trajectory (Hamm 1995). The technical improvements of the piano during the nineteenth century led to an evolution of the keyboard repertoire; the introduction of the electric guitar marked the transition from the big bands of the swing era to the leaner rhythm and blues groups. Similarly, the invention of Auto-Tune has transformed popular music over the past twenty-five years, populating our soundscape with perfectly pitched, shimmering robotic voices. The first epiphany of the effect – in Cher's “Believe”, in 1998 – has been regarded as a periodizing event. As Simon Reynolds (2018) writes in the quote given above, when Auto-Tune's

robotic glitch shatters Cher's voice at the line «So sa-a-ad that you're leaving», «what we were really "leaving" was the 20th century».

This interpretive mechanism is grounded in a form of «hard determinism» wherein technology is regarded as «an independent change agent, an autonomous force that exerts itself on society from the outside» (Prior 2018: 5). This top-down approach, in which innovations are conceptualized as unfolding along a trajectory “from the culture to the users”, is characteristic of both “apocalyptic” perspectives on mass culture and technoutopias. New technologies are essentialized, and treated as if they were external to the culture in which they are “created” and developed. This perspective can be contrasted with a «soft» and bottom-up determinism, which is a commonly held view in Anglophone cultural studies. Technology is accorded a certain level of agency: «it disrupts, changes, makes possible, creates, produces, undermine». However, it is essential to recognize that this agency «operates only in relation to complex and changing webs of production and use» (Prior 2018: 7; Taylor 2001).

The advent of the digital age has resulted in a significant transformation of the ecosystem in which music is produced and consumed. However, as anthropologist Georgina Born (2022: 1) has contended, the impact of digital technologies on music cannot be encapsulated within a single, unified account. Rather, the goal of scholars should be to «develop methods of tracing out and doing justice to the multiple ways in which music and the digital become enmeshed». Researchers must adopt an agnostic stance regarding the causal relationship between technology and music (Born 2022: 5), refraining from assuming that the connection linking presumed causes and supposed effects is straightforward. It is thus essential to examine «the cluster of social meanings and practices that surround [technology] in historically specific settings» (Prior 2018: 7). Similarly, the anthropological perspective on music posits that “music itself” is not “something” that can be influenced or modified by technology, but rather a series of practices performed by humans. The advent of digital technology has brought about notable qualitative and quantitative shifts in the way people make music, as humans and machines engage in intricate interactions. However, as Born (2022: 1) asserts, «the mediation of music cannot be reduced to its technological mediation alone – however world-changing [...] [new] technologies may appear to be».

In essence, while new sound technologies, such as Auto-Tune, undoubtedly have a major impact on music practices, their emergence should not be viewed as the sole driving force behind changes in musicking. Rather, the “pole” of musical practices (how people engage in music-making) and the “pole” of technologies (the devices people use to make music) interact in a complex feedback network. Although musical practices may appear to follow technologies, it is evident that new sound technologies are not developed in a vacuum. Rather, they emerge precisely as a response to existing music practices that are deeply embedded in their cultural context. Technologies manifest as «cultural units», often defined by an «identity crisis» encompassing all aspects of their «socially defined

existence» (Altman 2004: 19). The notion of “technology” is not a static entity, but rather a dynamic construct comprising a set of «complex cultural signs» (*ibidem*: 16). These symbols are not merely passive entities; rather, they are subject to interpretation and imbued with meanings and values by individuals, in accordance with their experiences and social position. Therefore, an investigation of Auto-Tune should not be primarily focused on its impact on music, but rather on how it is being utilized and interpreted by individuals and music communities. In other words, it should be examined as a component of contemporary musicking.

The concept of “affordance” – originally introduced by psychology and popularized by design studies, notably of software (Norman 1988, 1998) – is useful for conceptualizing the relationship between technology and practices without falling into determinism. The affordance of an artefact, whether hardware or software, can be defined as the relationship between the «object/technology and the use that enables or constrains potential behavioral outcomes in a particular context» (Evans et al. 2017: 36; Davis 2020). It is a matter of observing how the properties of an object (or technology) suggest and constrain its possible uses by a subject, endowed with certain capacities to interact with that object (or technology); in socio-semiological terms, a certain «musical competence» (Stefani 1982: 9). Stefani posits that there is a «capacity to produce meaning through and/or around music» that is «distributed and exercised in different ways and with different roles among the members of a culture» (*ibidem*: 10).¹ The concept of affordance, which emphasizes the role of subjects’ interaction with devices, is compatible with this approach, since «affordances are how objects shape action for socially situated subjects» (Davis 2020).

The concept of affordance does not appear to be a priority in the study of musical instruments (Tullberg 2022). For instance, it is absent from Cottrell’s recent collection (2024a), despite its use in the context of NIME (International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression; see, for example, Tanaka 2010). However, it appears to be associated with several tenets of organology. For example, the notion that there exists «a direct and strictly determined relationship between the material structure of the source and the sonic result» (Guizzi 2002: xix), and that musical instruments «constitute a sort of permanent materialization of the cultural conventions that regulate music and that oversee [...] the practices and behaviors that each [social group] enacts in the conscious production of the sounds that are its own» (*ibidem*; see also Staiti 2021; Schaeffner 1936). This consideration also appears to be pertinent to software used to make music. In this regard, Guizzi’s (2002: xx) observation that instruments present themselves not only «as producers of sounds», but also as «visualized sounds» is particularly relevant. In other words, there is an «apparatus of rules (natural and cultural, technical and social)» that is «largely embedded in the structure of an instrument» (*ibidem*: xxi), which, in fact, constitutes what a designer would define as an affordance.

¹ All translations from Italian are by the author.

3. Auto-Tune enters

Auto-Tune is a pitch correction software designed to modify the pitch of individual notes in a melody line, either in real time or post-production. The algorithm that forms the basis of Auto-Tune was initially developed by Exxon engineer Andy Hildebrand for mapping the presence of underground oil fields using sound impulses. Hildebrand himself soon realized that his work could be more effectively applied to music. The first version of the software was enthusiastically received at the 1997 NAMM show and was released by Antares shortly afterwards. In its early days, Auto-Tune was commercialized as a plugin, first for Mac and then for Windows, and later as a rack-mounted unit (the *Auto-Tune Intonation Processor ATR-1*). Almost immediately, the effect found its way into many recording studios because of its unprecedented capability to edit poor or non-professional vocal performances. This was clearly stated by one of the first reviewers, in August 1997:

Every studio owner will be familiar with the problem of the young band who come in to record a track, but then find that while their singer is full of passion, the pitching is at best dubious, and certainly not up to professional standards. [...] What's needed is a magic potion that will help singers stay in tune, without losing their expression or energy. To my knowledge, no such thing exists, but Antares Systems' AutoTune software comes a pretty close second. (White 1997)

The development and rapid diffusion of Auto-Tune can be explained in relation to the history of recorded music in the late 1990s. Starting in the 1980s, access to home recording technology became increasingly democratized (Théberge 1997). In the following decade, the widespread availability of personal computers and digital audio workstations opened the possibility of recording to non-professional musicians. Amateur and professional sound engineers needed recording tools that were user-friendly, cost-effective, time-efficient, and capable of maintaining a suitable level of quality. Auto-Tune emerged as a solution to these demands.

From the very first version of the software, Auto-Tune introduced a key affordance that remains a significant feature to this day: the option to utilize the effect in two distinct modes, each necessitating a different level of competence from the user and each capable of generating different results. The “Graphical Mode” shows «the detected pitch and allows [users] to draw in the desired pitch» on a display grid, with time on the horizontal axis and pitch on the vertical (Antares 2000a). This mode is suitable for fine-tuning individual parts and requires a certain amount of skill by the sound engineer, who can control every single parameter of the sound. Since 2001, the competitor software Melodyne has established itself in studios as an alternative to Auto-Tune for this purpose. In “Automatic Mode” – the operating mode with which Auto-Tune is most associated, and from which it derives the prefix “auto” in its brand name (Exarchos and Zagorski-Thomas 2020: 320) – the software automatically corrects the pitch according to the parameters

specified by the user via an interface. In the first release, users could select the key choosing between «major, minor, chromatic and 26 historical and microtonal scales» (Antares 2000a), «from an obscure ethnic scale to a simple chromatic type» (White 1997). It was also possible to modify individual scales, to exclude certain notes from the application of the effect, or to activate it only in response to certain inputs (for example, on the highest note of a melody, or on the target note of a complex interval). Later versions of Auto-Tune introduced additional features while maintaining consistency with the fundamental approach and configuration of the software's initial release.

The uniqueness of Auto-Tune compared to its competitors at the time, emphasized by both the official Antares website (2000a) and the reviewers (White 1997), lied in the “fidelity” achieved through its customization options. By setting the parameters correctly, it was possible to preserve the «natural scoops, swoops and vibrato» of the voice and avoid the «unnatural warbles and glitches» typical of pitch shifters on the market at the time (White 1997). The design rationale behind Auto-Tune, therefore, was that of *not* being heard. And indeed, in the period following its introduction, Auto-Tune represented a kind of “factory secret” of sound engineers, a trick that can make out-of-tune performers sing well while saving on the number of takes needed to close a recording session. A sort of sonic equivalent of Photoshop (Prior 2018: 136), to be used discreetly and whose presence was not only to remain unnoticed by the listener, but – possibly – even unknown to the singer.

4. «The Cher effect»

Cher's international hit “Believe”, released in October 1998, has a special place in the mythology of Auto-Tune as the first song to feature the effect. In fact, “Believe” is probably not the very first song to use Auto-Tune, but it is certainly the first to make it audible through an improper manipulation of its original functioning. In Automatic Mode, the first release of Auto-Tune incorporates three main faders: “Scale detune” (which alters the scale reference frequency), “Retune” and “Tracking” (Fig. 1).

The “Retune” function controls the speed at which the sound input is processed and adjusted to the target pitch. As the aforementioned review (White 1997) explains, «If this is set too fast, the process will start to strip out the human features of performance, such as slides up to notes, or vibrato». The “Tracking” parameter, whose settings span from “Choosy” to “Relaxed”, also has implications regarding the extent to which the result displays a human-like quality. When the setting is adjusted to the maximum level (“Choosy”), the software forces each note to the exact pitch, which may sound «a little artificial» (*ibidem*). In the case of performances that are significantly out of tune, Auto-Tune causes the pitch to oscillate rapidly between two notes «in a most unconvincing manner». The reviewer suggests that the effect is akin to «yodeling», and ironically comments: «Of course, if you're in the business of creating ethnic-sounding vocal samples, this can be a useful effect» (*ibidem*). It is, in an ironic twist, this very phenomenon that

FIGURE 1. Antares' Auto-Tune first interface, Automatic Mode (Antares 2000b).

we retrospectively recognize as the most typical and characterizing manifestation of Auto-Tune. Initially dubbed the “Cher effect” in honor of its popularizer, it is then more simply referred to as the “Auto-Tune effect”.

Despite Auto-Tune’s initial purpose of assisting users in achieving a performance that sounds “natural”, the affordances of its initial release make it considerably easier to generate this kind of weird sounds. In order to “conceal” the effect, some familiarity with the various parameters and their functions is necessary. The triggering of a robotic voice can be achieved simply by moving upwards two of the three principal faders. Such use was not foreseen by the developers, including Hildebrand, who included that setting «just for kicks» (Provenzano 2019: 4), assuming that «No one in their right mind would ever use [it]» (CBC 2016).

The most extreme and original results are achieved when Auto-Tune is configured in this manner and applied to a vocal line that oscillates seamlessly between multiple pitches. Specifically, an Auto-Tune setting with maximum tracking and retune speed (i.e., with the faders up), attempting to “extract” a precise pitch from a glissando, portamento, or melisma with great rapidity, will transform them into a scale or embellishment (albeit a somewhat arbitrary one) by discretizing them into single notes. The speed of execution of these notes is a function of the latency time required for the software to process a pitch that is judged to be “incorrect”, but which changes in real time. This is a form of digital musicking that involves the interaction of human voices and machines, and it is based upon an element of *alea*.

FIGURE 2. Spectrogram: «So sa-a-a-ad», Cher, “Believe (Acapella)”. Instead of the continuous, curving lines that would be found in a normal vocal pattern, we find here a series of broken straight lines.

During the “Believe” recording sessions, Cher deliberately sought to achieve a robotic voice for expressive purposes. Her producer Mark Taylor, who had recently equipped himself with Auto-Tune, had the idea of testing the new effect.

I called Mark – can we do it into a vocoder? He said, I just got this thing called a pitch machine, and I’m playing around with it. I went in later to listen and we both just jumped out of our chairs and high-fived. I said, you don’t even know it’s me! He said, Well, that’s what I was afraid of. I said, No, it’s perfect. I love this. (Ryzik 2023)

Cher is also said to have resisted the record company’s attempts to eliminate those unconventional sounds: «You can change that part of it over my dead body!» (Strauss 1999).

In the verses of the song, Auto-Tune intervenes on several short *portamenti* and melismas, changing them into a sequence of single notes: for example, on the short passage Cher performs on the “a” of the verse «So sa-a-a-ad [that you’re leaving]», as evidenced by the spectrogram of the vocal part (Fig. 2). The artificial, robotic quality imparted by Auto-Tune to the verse passages is also highlighted in the music video by a glitch in the image, which seems to mirror the audio effect.

In the months following the success of “Believe”, some reviewers erroneously attributed the “Cher effect” to a vocoder. This interpretation was reinforced by the attempted misleading of the song’s producers, who sought to maintain the secrecy surrounding the use of Auto-Tune in the recording process (Brøvig-Hanssen & Danielsen 2016: 119). Actually, it soon became obvious that the “Cher effect” cannot be replicated without the use of Auto-Tune, as vocoder processes audio in a different manner (Provenzano 2018: 153). A vocoder is an electronic musical instrument that has the capacity to transform

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kKEUHy97-LA&ab_channel=NinaHagen>; accessed: 1 July 2024.

a sound input (specifically, the voice) into electronic information, which can be utilized to pilot a vocal synthesizer. In contrast, when Auto-Tune is employed in Automatic Mode, the pitch correction engages with the voice in real time, thereby enabling the voice itself to exert direct control on the effect, although with an element of chance. Of course, it is also possible to achieve a similar result by re-amping the voice track, that is, through the real-time processing of a pre-existing voice recording (this is likely the case with “Believe”). These features set Auto-Tune apart from other devices that modify the human voice, as it is unique in its ontological, phenomenological, and affordance-related characteristics.

5. Creative vs. cosmetic: discourses around Auto-Tune

The presence of Auto-Tune in contemporary popular music gives rise to a multiplicity of manifestations, discourses, production practices, and applications. From a phenomenological perspective, it is possible to identify two primary sonic manifestations of Auto-Tune. Firstly, there is its explicit and overt presence, in which the human voice is transformed into a synthetic and unnatural-sounding entity. In contrast, when utilized as a pitch corrector, Auto-Tune is potentially undetectable and (apparently) transparent. The voice is in tune, the effect is inaudible.

From the perspective of sound production, two distinct applications of Auto-Tune can be distinguished: a real-time use, whereby the effect is incorporated by the performer as an organic element of the performance; and a post-production use, whereby the effect is applied during the editing or mixing phase. In the first case, Auto-Tune functions at the input level. Singers shape their vocal performances based on the feedback they receive (via the ear monitor) from their processed voice, engaging in a digital musicking where the auditory output is the result of the interplay between human and machine elements. In the second case, the effect is employed at the output level to modify a pre-existing musical performance, frequently by a party other than the performer (the producer, the sound engineer).

The various manifestations of Auto-Tune (audible versus inaudible) and the diverse applications of the effect (real-time versus studio editing) are frequently structured in a dialectical opposition within the context of reception and the discourses surrounding Auto-Tune. On the one hand, there are the “creative” uses: Auto-Tune is employed as a sound effect, as an expressive choice (or is interpreted as such). On the other, the “cosmetic” uses: Auto-Tune is applied to correct, mask, improve an inaccurate performance (or is interpreted as such). In the latter case, discourses regarding Auto-Tune are predominantly critical, often describing it as a tool of capitalism whose objective is «to produce a commercially viable product for a mass audience – pop songs – as fast as possible» (Åkervall 2021: 81).

Indeed, the distinction between creative and cosmetic uses lies at an interpretive (and

thus ideological) level, rather than being rooted in objective data. It is therefore crucial to ask at what point «our auditory perception transcend[s] from pitch-only to textural appreciation» (Exarchos and Zagorski-Thomas 2020: 320). The question of whether an autotuned voice can be considered “creative” and/or “appreciated” hinges on a number of factors, including our own positioning towards the performer, the performer’s gender (Provenzano 2019), the musical genre of the performance, and so forth. The concept of “creativity” – as well as popular music aesthetics in general – is deeply intertwined with ideologies of authenticity, which tend to value the “true” over the “false”; and modernist ideologies, which tend to value what is “new” and “original” over what is “already heard” and “banal”.

In the interpretive frame provided by ideologies of authenticity, which is prevalent in the value construction of popular music and extensively discussed in the bibliography (Moore 2002; Middleton 1995, 2006; Mayhew 1999; Weisethaunet and Lindberg 2010) Auto-Tune is understood as a technology that enables the concealment of the “real performer”, modifying their voice or enabling individuals with limited vocal abilities to sing. These are the same accusations that have been made against Auto-Tune by its detractors since the software’s earliest days. For instance, in 2010 *Time Magazine* included Auto-Tune among the «50 worst inventions of the modern era», alongside such controversial items as subprime mortgages, DDT, Crocs, pop-up ads, Segway, and New Coke, and described it as a «a technology that can make bad singers sound good and really bad singers [...] sound like robots» (Fletcher 2010). However, the concepts of “real performer” or “(really) bad singer” in the context of popular music are inherently ideological. The “truth” of a performer is invariably shaped through performative strategies, which may even encompass not singing in tune, or singing “badly” (this is the case with folk revival: Tomatis 2023: 91, 96). Therefore, it is challenging to identify objective criteria for evaluating the quality of singing in the context of a «studio art recording» (Turino 2008), which is the culmination of numerous editing and post-production stages involving the performer’s voice.

In the interpretive frame of modernist ideologies, Auto-Tune is regarded as a worn-out and overused solution, given its pervasive presence in contemporary popular music. This is the position that had rock producer Steve Albini among its champions:

When things are overused in production, they come off as a clumsy cliché of an era. The blatant auto-tune was a charming gimmick then it became ubiquitous, then mandatory, then tedious and clichéd (Steve Albini in Mackintosh H. 2021).

As Provenzano (2019: 65) notes, the perception of Auto-Tune as a mere cosmetic device rather than a genuine creative tool has been linked, in the discourses of critics, music professionals, and the public, with a feminine trope. Provenzano references an interview by Hildebrand himself, who explains the function of Auto-Tune with the line: «To mo-

dify something isn't necessarily evil, my wife wears makeup!»; and by a studio technician, who asserts: «No woman wants to go to a party without makeup on». From Provenzano's feminist perspective, Auto-Tune is therefore understood as a device that allows for the «non-consensual tuning» (*ibidem*: 69) of the female voice, which in the context of contemporary pop music is expected to meet unrealistic standards of perfection. As a result, Auto-Tune can be regarded as a device that perpetuates the exploitation of female labor and female bodies (*ibidem*: 71). Conversely, this same prejudice does not extend to male artists, as evidenced by the presence of similar practices in musical genres, such as rap or indie, where «male performers have succeeded, artistically and commercially, at employing the expressive range Auto-Tune promises without the nagging underlying question of their somehow actual ability» (*ibidem*: 76).

6. Auto-Tune and the pop voice

Rather than representing alternative applications of the same technology, the various manifestations and uses of Auto-Tune can be seen as the two extreme points on a “vocal effects continuum” that includes other effects that are normally used in conjunction with Auto-Tune, such as delays, reverbs, doubling and compression, and that shape the sound of contemporary pop voices. This is once more exemplified by the case of “Believe”. The verse passages in which Cher's voice “breaks” in its digital melismas serve a functional role in the construction of the song, launching an epic chorus in which the voice “cleans up” in the high register, in correspondence with the main hook («Do you believe in life after love?»). The stark contrast between the human-sounding voice in the chorus and the glitches in the verses was undoubtedly a significant factor in the success of the song. Nevertheless, even the “human” voice is the consequence of the interaction between a vocal performance and a series of effects designed to modify it (and which may also include Auto-Tune used as a pitch corrector). However, in the second case, the voice is not perceived as being particularly processed. Or, rather, it is not heard as such, due to the pervasiveness of autotuned and effected voices in the popular music soundscape. And yet, «pitch manipulation, even at its most discreet, results in textural artefacts of different shades on the scale of perceptibility», which in turn influence the vocal timbre (Exarchos & Zagorski-Thomas 2020: 323). In the years following the success of “Believe”, a new standard of mainstream pop emerged, characterized by a distinctively unnatural, “glossy”, and almost inhuman (or posthuman) voices. The use of Auto-Tune, along with other common vocal effects, has become a prevalent practice in contemporary pop music, shaping the “new normal” of vocal performance.

A survey in the pop voices of the years following Cher's success confirms how overt and covert uses, and performative and productive uses, can coexist within the same song, and how it is challenging – and futile – to distinguish one from the other. For example, in a song such as Britney Spears' “Piece of Me” (2007), Auto-Tune is apparently em-

FIGURE 3. Spectrogram: «Under my umbrella-elah-elah eh eh eh», Rihanna “Umbrella (Acapella Studio Version)”.² In the lower right corner, the distinctive straight lines generated by Auto-Tune can be observed.

ployed to distance the singer’s “real person” from her “artistic person”, thereby offering a critique of Spears’ pop star status, as «the singer’s objectification appears to be spectacularly performed through various vocal tricks (including Auto-Tune) that highlight her mass-mediated commodification» (Prior 2009: 137). In essence, Auto-Tune is used to reverse the «authenticity trope», whereby «the self-conscious artifice became the new authenticity» (Middleton 2006: 207). This can be defined as the act of presenting oneself as “inauthentic”, while simultaneously demonstrating an awareness of the artifice involved (see also: Keightley 2001). In Rihanna’s 2009 single “Umbrella”, it is evident that Auto-Tune is employed to “correct” and regularize various sections of the song, including the hook («Under my umbrella-elah-elah eh eh eh...»). This can be readily discerned by examining the a cappella version’s spectrogram (Fig. 3). But it is equally clear that the unique vocal color of that passage is deliberately generated by the singer in interaction with the effect. Rihanna appears to “chew” the vowels with apparent ease, experimenting with the digitized sound of her voice, whose «Barbados grain [...] harmonizes well with the nasal tinge of Auto-Tune» (Reynolds 2018).

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7Hd7pCA0MV&ab_channel=ZachOakes> (accessed: 1 July 2024).

One of the few ethnographies available on the use of Auto-Tune in the studio (Provenzano 2019) demonstrates how the effect has long since been employed as a creative tool even in the compositional phase, to facilitate the elaboration of vocal parts. In several «writing sessions, Auto-Tune is on, they [the singers] sing through it [...] So it actually like helps them find melodies sometimes» (Provenzano 2019: 76).

Numerous contemporary practices thus involve Auto-Tune being permanently activated. Singers hear their already processed voice through headphones and adjust their vocal performance accordingly. The distinction between the human and machine components of the audible output is effectively dissolved, rendering them inextricable and indistinguishable. Some vocalists even «insist on [their autotuned voice] being printed so nobody can hear how they sing without [Auto-Tune]» (*ibidem*). This same process is now a standard component of live performances as well. When utilized in real-time, Auto-Tune's affordances therefore exert a profound influence on the way performers sing, establishing a continuous feedback loop between their vocal abilities, preferences, and sensibilities. For instance, some «vocalists have learned to bend with the effect, exploiting the supersmooth sheen it lends to long sustained notes, and intuitively singing slightly flat because that triggers over-correction in Auto-Tune pleasingly» (Reynolds 2018).

Additionally, the ubiquitous presence of autotuned voices seems to be available as a stylistic model to be imitated even “upstream” of the effect itself. The extreme case is represented by those performers who try to replicate Auto-Tune's digital “yodeling” through vocal techniques, for instance YouTuber Emma Robinson (Reynolds 2018). A more fascinating area of inquiry would be to examine how some vocalists seemingly incorporate stylistic embellishments and techniques that appear to emulate the way Auto-Tune interacts with the human voice. This could be the result of a purely stylistic fascination, or it could be a kind of “laryngeal memory” of performances enhanced by Auto-Tune, which may lead to their replication even in the absence the vocal processor. Further research is required to gain a deeper understanding of this specific matter. One illustrative example might be that of Italian singer Mahmood. In its hit song “Soldi” (2019), upon executing an embellishment on the “i” of «soldi», Mahmood chooses to perform a rapid descending scale (g / f# / e), which appears to evoke the sonic outcomes of Auto-Tune when applied to a *portamento*. In a live cappella version of the same song,⁴ Mahmood replicates the effect.

Auto-Tune is therefore influencing and shaping contemporary approaches to singing. The most appropriate comparison is with the popularization of the microphone technology in the 1930s-1940s: just as its affordances enabled and facilitated the development of a new range of vocal styles (including whispered and expressive techniques, such as “crooning”), the affordances of Auto-Tune are shaping the way we sing and listen to pop

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TDe1bvH4t0U&ab_channel=LaRepubblica> (accessed: 1 July 2024).

voices in the twenty-first century.

7. «Searching for the music in your speech»

Shortly after the success of “Believe”, Auto-Tune began to be applied in a different way that was not foreseen by its developers, but – again – encouraged by the software’s affordances. It started to be used not to manipulate melody lines, but to alter speech, especially in rap music and in the rap sections of pop songs. The earliest example of this usage can be identified in a track by Italian dance music band Eiffel 65, “Too Much of Heaven” (Reynolds 2018), included on the 1999 album *Europop* and released as a single the following year. This results in an unprecedented sonic quality of the voice. The software forces linguistic intonation to precise pitches, resulting in a cyborg-like voice that still retains a recognizable human quality. Applying the effect to speech pitch increases the degree of uncertainty in the resulting outcome, independently of whether the effect is employed in real time or at the production stage. This is a key factor contributing to the appeal of Auto-Tune for performers. One of the first attempts at theorizing this fascination can be attributed to Thom Yorke, the lead singer of Radiohead. Yorke employed Auto-Tune in two tracks on the band’s 2001 album, *Amnesiac*: “Pulk/Pull Revolving Doors” and “Packt Like Sardines in a Crushd Tin Box”.

There’s also this trick you can do [...], where you give the machine a key and then you just talk into it. It desperately tries to search for the music in your speech, and produces notes at random. If you’ve assigned it a key, you’ve got music (Thom Yorke in Reynolds 2001: 26).

In a significant number of rap tracks released in the subsequent years, however, Auto-Tune also began to be used to develop melodic lines, progressively liberating the MC from his “traditional” role and blurring the distinction between sung and rapped sections: «melody became democratized, as MCs were suddenly able to sing on tracks even if they were actually unable to hold a note» (Mackintosh K. 2021). The first musician to associate with this trend, the very “face” of Auto-Tune in commercial rap, was T-Pain. In the latter half of the 2000s, the effect became so closely associated with his persona and vocal identity that, in 2009, the iPhone app *I Am T-Pain* (a cheap Auto-Tune emulator) was made available. In the same year, the musician introduced the effect to the general American public in a sketch on Ellen DeGeneres’ highly popular talk show.

While T-Pain has frequently been criticized for his excessive and cheesy use of Auto-Tune, Reynolds (2018) notes that, during the same period, the effect was used by other rappers, including Lil Wayne and Kanye West, «to really make something artistic». West, in particular, made extensive use of Auto-Tune in his acclaimed 2008 album *808s and Heartbreak*, where the effect is associated with intimate and emotional lyrics, in which the depersonalization of the voice seems to become «the aural equivalent of a trembling

lip or twitching eyelid» (*ibidem*). Auto-Tune was therefore used «to express alienation, sadness, or loss» (Brøvig-Hanssen & Danielsen 2016: 120) reinforcing a «pop-cultural association of a robotic voice with emotional distance or flatness» (*ibidem*: 124). The idea of the autotuned singer as a «brokenhearted android» (*ibidem*: 117), whose voice exists at the intersection of the bodily and the synthetic, also pervades the music of one of the most influential American indie folk artists of the same period, Bon Iver. The singer-songwriter combined the effect with minimal guitar arrangements or even used it in a cappella songs. One example is “Woods” from 2009, which was later sampled by Kanye West for his track “Lost in the World”.

While Auto-Tune was granted a certain degree of acceptance by critics, at least in the context of its use by male artists for “creative” purposes, a segment of the hip-hop community demonstrated a clear aversion. In this regard, Jay-Z’s track “D.O.A. Death of Auto-Tune” (2009) is a compelling example, a song manifesto in support of the restoration of “old” rap, conceived as a word-centered art form. Auto-Tune is described as a technology that compromises the authenticity of hip hop, because «raps don’t have melodies».

This is anti Auto-Tune, death of the ring-tone,
 This ain’t for iTunes, this ain’t for sing alongs
 [...]

 My raps don’t have melodies
 This shit make niggas wan’ go and commit felonies.

Rappers using Auto-Tune are accused of «singing too much» and «t-paining too much» («Get back to rap you t-paining too much»); namely, of not being “authentic”. They are described as effeminate («Put your skirt back down, grow a set man»), confirming Provenzano’s (2018, 2019) thesis about gender distinctions in the use of Auto-Tune, and, more generally, the association of female tropes with inauthenticity in pop music (Mayhew 1999). Nevertheless, Jay-Z’s stance represents a rearguard effort. Over the past decade, Auto-Tune has become a central stylistic element in rap music, particularly within the Southern rap and trap scenes, and has redefined the boundaries of rap vocals. In such contexts, Auto-Tune’s capacity to “search for the music in the speech” has been exercised to the fullest.

8. Playing (with) Auto-Tune

Since the 2010s, several performers have been moving away from the conventional style of rap, distancing themselves «from the internal rhyme oversaturation» associated with the classical MC figure and adopting a more fragmented flow. Kit Mackintosh (2021) refers to this phenomenon, exemplified by the musical group Migos (e.g., “Versace”, 2013),

as «frag rap». In parallel, a closely related trend has emerged, referred to as “Soundcloud rap”, which takes its name from the digital platform on which this micro-genre gained visibility in the early 2010s (Philips 2021: 125). Subsequently, it is also referred to as “mumble rap”: the term is evidently derogatory, referring to the unintelligible slurring of its early performers, in particular, Future, as exemplified by the track “Tony Montana” (2011) (Mackintosh K. 2021). The term also retains a reference to the consumption of codeine-based drugs, central to trap culture, which result in a difficulty in articulating words. In the sign of this practice – rapping under the influence of codeine, or imitating the slurred speech typical of a person under the influence of this substance, while using Auto-Tune – mumble rappers are moving in an entirely new direction, «doing away with traditional ideas of MC craft (clear diction, extended narratives, referentially dense lyrics)» (Mackintosh K. 2021). In contrast, their lyrics are characterized by a lack of semantic content, with a tendency towards a drawling vocal delivery. Of particular significance is the function of ad-libs, common to many black music genres. Ad-libs are short verbal punctuations (such as “Uh”, “Yeah”, “Huh?”, “What!?”), a component of the extensive range of vocal techniques used in performances, including «moans, groans, yells, screams, shouts, shifts in sonority» (Wilson 1992: 160), and are typically employed to fill the pauses in the musical flow, or to engage in call-and-response. Filtered through Auto-Tune, ad-libs move from background to foreground, becoming the defining element of a new generation of rappers for whom «the entire game had changed» (Philips 2021: 126). In fact, what these performers seem to be doing is playing Auto-Tune through their own voices. In mumble rap and similar genres «Auto-Tune becomes frantic and convulsive», it «rapidly oscillates between different notes as it desperately scrabbles to latch onto a stable pitch, meaning that vocals tremble and undulate with a completely artificial vibrato» (Mackintosh K. 2021).

Mumble rappers’ approach to vocals is all about exploring and accentuating the feel and the internal architecture of their oral cavities in combination with the intensified texturing effects of Auto-Tune. A croak in the back of a performer’s throat, for instance, will leap out and get set alight by the effect so that it’s roaring and distorting, or a bit of spluttering will suddenly feel turbo-charged, becoming radiant and radioactive in the listener’s ear (Mackintosh K. 2021).

This tendency to “chew on words” to trigger the Auto-Tune effect was already detectable in some of its uses in pop music (as in Rihanna’s “Umbrella”). However, in the case of mumble rap and related genres, it has been carried to the point of rendering the lyrics almost unintelligible. Now «the flow [is] more like a musical instrument than a medium for a message» (Phillips 2021: 126). Notable examples include tracks by Migos (“Cocoon”, 2016), Lil Uzi Vert (“XO Tour Llif3”, 2017), Future (“Fuck Up Some Commas”, 2015) or Huncho Jack, a collaborative effort between Travis Scott and Migos’ Quavo (“Hun-

cho Jack”, “Black and Chinese”, 2017). Autotuned rappers have been evolving beyond rap – many of them do not even consider themselves rap musicians (Phillips 2021: 125) – in the direction of a «vocal psychedelia» (Mackintosh K. 2021). While breakthroughs in synthesizer and sampling technology have been the source of musical innovation in recent decades, digitally processed voice can now be recognized as the new frontier (Mackintosh K. 2021). Mackintosh and other enthusiasts of this new trend, again, adhere to modernist ideologies in evaluating popular music, but they reverse the perspective of Auto-Tune’s critics. Now Auto-Tune represents the “new”, the future, in contrast to pop culture theories that emphasize «retromania» and the role of the past in contemporary music cultures (Reynolds 2011).

Both Simon Reynolds (2021) and Kit Mackintosh (2021) have correctly inscribed Auto-Tune in the history of black music. The novel applications of Auto-Tune that emerge in trap and mumble rap exhibit close affinities with analogous uses that traverse many Afro-descendant music genres in other parts of the world in the same years. These include Jamaican bashment, and several nascent electronic genres from Africa and the Caribbean. Reynolds, in the wake of Gilroy (1993), proposes the concept of a «new revised Black Atlantic», where everything «takes place within an eight-sided polygon that connects Lagos, London, Brooklyn, Atlanta, Houston, Kingston, Montego Bay, and Port of Spain» (Reynolds 2021). This «digital diaspora», with «YouTube being preeminent as a vector» for the dissemination of sound and images, results in musical subcultures that are at the same time «intensely territorialized» and «globalized» (*ibidem*).

Contextualized within the broader cultural landscape, the autotuned “vocal psychedelia” of trap, mumble rap, bashment, and related genres can thus be interpreted as the latest iteration in a long tradition of African-based musical practices that use the voice as an instrument, or as a means of imitating an instrument. The manifestations of this way of “playing” Auto-Tune – a sort of bubbling flood of digital glitches – align with the concept of the «heterogeneous sound ideal» outlined by Wilson (1992: 159-160). This “ideal” is seen by Wilson as a fundamental element in the core underlying conceptions that shape the definition of African and African American music. The expression defines «a common approach to music making in which a kaleidoscopic range of dramatically contrasting qualities of sound (timbre) is sought after in both vocal and instrumental music», and where «the desirable musical sound texture is one that contains a combination of diverse timbres» (Wilson 1992: 160). Auto-Tune, originally developed as a tool for correcting and standardizing intonation, has thus been employed – in some of its most radical contemporary applications – in a manner that is completely opposed to its original purpose. These applications involve the avoidance of cleanliness and sound accuracy, the digital manipulation and distortion of audio signals, and the introduction of “undesirable” characteristics into vocals.

9. Conclusions

A number of musical practices that make use of Auto-Tune, whether in the context of pop vocals or rap, and the nascent field of “vocal psychedelia”, share a common feature: Auto-Tune is always “on”, both in the recording studio and in live performances. Auto-Tune is now embodied in the vocal identity of numerous performers, to the point that their non-autotuned voice simply does not exist. Performers do not just sing or rap through Auto-Tune, but *with* Auto-Tune, interacting with its structural features in a feedback loop. What we hear is a hybrid between the human voice and its digital re-processing that resists the reduction of its elements to discrete components. In edge cases – those that Kit Mackintosh (2021) associates with the category of “vocal psychedelia” – performers even seem to be *playing* Auto-Tune, using the voice as the primary input to trigger the effect, with the objective of achieving a result that is the antithesis of the original Antares’ factory specifications.

The latest applications of Auto-Tune suggest that the effect, in addition to being included in the long history of voice modification devices, can be regarded as a musical instrument in its own right. From the perspective of organology, Auto-Tune could be conceptualized as a «closed loop» between the software – or rather the «parts of the artefact which are used to control the sound» – and the performer’s body through the medium of voice (Cottrell 2024b: 11; Kvifte 2008). This perspective enables a shift in focus towards the affordances of the device, since a musical instrument is only capable of producing sound in interaction with the performer’s manipulation. Indeed, the very concept of “instrument” is a misleading one, as Staiti (2021: 12) argues, building upon Schaeffner (1936). The term “instrument” denotes a function that is subsidiary to music. Like poetry, music arises from materials that can be shaped and transformed by human agency (Staiti 2021: 12). In other words, the phenomenon we refer to as “music” arises from the pathways of manipulation that emerge from the forms themselves and the processes through which they are transformed by performers. The conceptualization of Auto-Tune – a device for making music that is not a musical instrument – therefore represents a significant theoretical challenge, one that is central to understanding contemporary musicking, along with the myriads of effected voices that populate the soundscape of the twenty-first century.

References

- Altman, Rick
2004 *Silent Film Sound*, New York, Columbia University Press.
- Åkervall, Lisa
2021 “The Auto-Tuned Self: Modulating Voice and Gender in Digital Media Ecologies”, *Camera Obscura* 107, XXXVI/2: 65-97.
- Antares
2000a “Auto-Tune”, Antares official website, www.antarestech.com, 11 May; retrieved with web.archive: <<https://web.archive.org/web/20000511074540/http://www.antarestech.com:80/files/autotune.html>>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
2000b “Auto-Tune - Automatic mode”, Antares official website, www.antarestech.com, 4 February; retrieved with <web.archive: https://web.archive.org/web/20000304192205/http://www.antarestech.com/files/at_auto.html>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
- Brøvig-Hanssen, Ragnhild & Anne Danielsen
2016 *Digital Signatures. The Impact of Digitization on Popular Music Sound*, Cambridge, The MIT Press.
- CBC
2016 “How Andy Hildebrand changed the music industry with Auto-Tune”, *CBC*, 24 October; <[https://www.cbc.ca/radio/q/schedule-for-monday-october-24-2016-1.3815495/how-andy-hildebrand-changed-the-music-industry-with-auto-tune-1.3818443#:~:text=%22No%20one%20in%20their%20right,it's%20a%20pretty%20distinguishable%20sound%20](https://www.cbc.ca/radio/q/schedule-for-monday-october-24-2016-1.3815495/how-andy-hildebrand-changed-the-music-industry-with-auto-tune-1.3818443#:~:text=%22No%20one%20in%20their%20right,it's%20a%20pretty%20distinguishable%20sound%20;)>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
- Cottrell, Stephen
2024a (ed.) *The Cultural Study of Musical Instruments - An Overview. Shaping Sound and Society*, London & New York, Routledge.
2024b “Introduction”, in Stephen Cottrell (ed.), *The Cultural Study of Musical Instruments - An Overview. Shaping Sound and Society*, London & New York, Routledge: 1-28.
- Davis, Jenny L.
2020 *How Artifacts Afford. The Power and Politics of Everyday Things*, Cambridge, The MIT Press.
- Hamm, Charles
1995 “Modernist Narratives and Popular Music”, in *Putting Popular Music in its Place*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press: 1-40.
- Evans, Sandra K., Katy E. Pearce, Jessica Vitak, & Jeffrey W. Treem
2017 “Explicating Affordances: A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Affordances in Communication Research”, *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* XXII/1: 35-52.
- Exarchos, Michail (aka Stereo Mike) and Simon Zagorski-Thomas
2020 “Audio Processing”, in Andrew Bourbon and Simon Zagorski-Thomas (eds.), *The Bloomsbury Handbook of Music Production*, New York, Bloomsbury: 317-336.
- Fletcher, Dan
2010 “The 50 Worst Inventions – Auto-Tune”, *Time*, 17 May; <https://content.time.com/time/specials/packages/article/0,28804,1991915_1991909_1991903,00.html>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
- Gilroy, Paul
1993 *The Black Atlantic: Modernity and Double Consciousness*, London, Verso.

- Guizzi, Febo
 2002 *Guida alla musica popolare in Italia – 3. Gli strumenti*, Lucca, Libreria musicale italiana.
- Kvifte, Tellef
 2008 “What is a Musical Instrument?”, *Svensk Tidskrift for Musikforskning*, XC/1: 45-56.
- Mackintosh, Hamish
 2021 “Classic Interview: Steve Albini”, *Music Radar*, 23 July [originally published in 2013]; <<https://www.musicradar.com/news/steve-albini-interview>>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
- Mackintosh, Kit
 2021 *Neon Screams: How Drill, Trap and Bashment Made Music New Again*, London, Repeater Books [ebook].
- Mayhew, Emma
 1999 “Women in Popular Music and the Construction of ‘Authenticity’”, *Journal of Interdisciplinary Gender Studies*, IV/1: 63-81.
- Middleton, Richard
 1995 “Authorship, Gender and the Construction of Meaning in The Eurythmics’ Hit Recordings”, *Cultural Studies*, IX/3: 465-85.
 2006 *Voicing the Popular. On the Subjects in Popular Music*, London and New York, Routledge.
- Moore, Allan
 2002 “Authenticity as Authentication”, *Popular music*, XXI/2: 209-23.
- Norman, Donald
 1988 *The Psychology of Everyday Things*, New York, Basic Books.
 1998 *The Design of Everyday Things*, Cambridge, MIT Press.
- Phillips, Matthew T.
 2021 “Soundcloud Rap and Alien Creativity. Transforming Rap and Popular Music through Mumble Rap”, *Journal of Popular Music Studies*, XXXIII/3: 125-44.
- Prior, Nick
 2009 “Software Sequencers and Cyborg Singers: Popular Music in the Digital Hypermodern”, *New Formations*, LXVI/1: 81-99.
 2018 *Popular Music, Digital Technology and Society*, London, Sage.
- Provenzano, Catherine
 2018 “Auto-Tune, Labor, and the Pop-Music Voice”, in Robert Fink, Melinda Latour and Zachary Wallmark (eds.), *The Relentless Pursuit of Tone: Timbre in Popular Music*, New York, Oxford University Press, 159-81.
 2019 “Making Voices. The Gendering of Pitch Correction and the Auto-Tune Effect in Contemporary Pop Music”, *Journal of Popular Music Studies*, XXXI/2: 63-84.
- Reynolds, Simon
 2001 “Walking on Thin Ice”, *The Wire* 209, 26-33.
 2011 *Retromania: Pop Culture’s Addiction to Its Own Past*, London, Faber & Faber.
 2018 “How Auto-Tune Revolutionized the Sound of Popular Music”, *Pitchfork*, September 17, <<https://pitchfork.com/features/article/how-auto-tune-revolutionized-the-sound-of-popular-music>>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
 2021 “Foreword”, in Kit Mackintosh, *Neon Screams: How Drill, Trap and Bashment Made Music New Again*, London, Repeater Books.
- Ryzik, Melena
 2023 “Cher on Her First Christmas LP, a New Beau and 25 Years of ‘Believe’”, *The New York Times*, 17 October, <<https://www.nytimes.com/2023/10/17/arts/music/cher-christmas.html>>; accessed: 1 July 2024.

- Schaeffner, André
1936 *Origine des instruments de musique; introduction ethnographique à l'histoire de la musique instrumentale*, Payot, Paris.
- Small, Christopher
1998 *Musicking. The Meaning of Performing and Listening*, Middletown, Wesleyan University Press.
- Staiti, Nico
2021 *Tenui meditabor harundine. Tiritera su titiri, totare, tituelle, calamauli e cerauli*, Palermo, Edizioni Museo Pasqualino.
- Stefani, Gino
1982 *La competenza musicale*, Bologna, Clueb.
- Strauss, Neil
1999 “Cher Resurrected, Again, by a Hit; The Long, Hard but Serendipitous Road to ‘Believe’”, *The New York Times*, 11 March, <<https://www.nytimes.com/1999/03/11/arts/cher-resurrected-again-by-a-hit-the-long-hard-but-serendipitous-road-to-believe.html>>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
- Tanaka, Atau
2010 “Mapping Out Instruments, Affordances, and Mobiles”, *Proceedings of the 2010 Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME 2010)*, Sydney, Australia: 89-93.
- Théberge, Paul
1997 *Any Sound You Can Imagine. Making Music/Consuming Technology*, Hanover, Wesleyan University Press.
- Titon, Todd Jeff
2008 “The Music Culture as a World of Music”, in Todd Jeff Titon (ed.), *Worlds of Music. An Introduction to the Music of the World's Peoples*, New York, Schirmer: 1-32.
- Tomatis, Jacopo
2023 *Nuovo Canzoniere Italiano's Bella Ciao*, New York, Bloomsbury.
- Tullberg, Markus
2022 “Affordances of Musical Instruments: Conceptual Consideration”, *Frontiers in Psychology*, doi 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.974820.
- Turino, Thomas
2008 *Music as Social Life: The Politics of Participation*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- Weisethaunet, Hans and Ulf Lindberg
2010 “Authenticity Revisited: The Rock Critic and the Changing Real”, *Popular Music and Society*, XXXIII/4: 465-85.
- White, Paul
1997 “Antares System Auto-tune. Digidesign Pro Tools TDM Pitch Correction Plug-in”, in *Sound on Sound*, August; <<https://www.soundonsound.com/reviews/antares-system-auto-tune>>; accessed: 1 July 2024.
- Wilson, Olly
1992 “The Heterogeneous Sound Ideal in African-American Music”, in Gena Dangel Caponi (ed.), *Signifyin(g), Sanctifyin', & SlamDunking. A Reader in African American Expressive Culture*, Amherst, University of Massachusetts Press: 157-71.